

Research

Financial Development and Economic Growth: The Evidence of Sri Lanka

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Abstract: Individual countries and panels of countries have been studied the association between financial development and economic growth using different methodologies. There are three kinds of results — first one unidirectional relationship second one bidirectional relationship and third one no relationship at all. Studies of Sri Lanka have insufficient; there have different ideas of conclusions and one unique method they have applied the papers. The purpose of the paper is to realize the relationship between financial development and economic growth in Sri Lanka. The annual data sets are used in 1947 to 2016 period of the Sri Lankan economy. This thesis has ten variables that can be obtained from the Central Bank Reports of Sri Lanka from 1950 to 2016. In this thesis, the unit root test, the vector error correction model (VECM) and the Chow test method are used to perform the tasks. In between short and long-term decisions, it can be used VECM and, eventually, by economic or political policy changes or unexpected economic shocks, can be used chow tests. The study found that the causal relationship between Money Supply (M2), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), Consumer Price Index (CPI), Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR) to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). There are no short-term causal relationships from Loans (loans), Government Debt (GD), Current account balances (CAB), Consumer Price Indices (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate to the Gross Domestic Product. The conclusion of the objective reaffirms that M2 and economic stability are of great importance in Sri Lanka. The factors that affect Sri Lanka's long-term financial development and economic growth are then identified. Developing Sri Lanka as a Financial Center, it will be a catalyst for economic growth and greater international trade. So, involvement Financial Center and Port City, Sri Lanka can be maximized their economic growth and financial development.

Keywords: GDP, VECM, Financial, Development, M2 .

Introduction

At the time of regaining independence, Sri Lanka was mainly an agricultural economy. The production of and trade in three plantation crops, viz., tea, rubber, and coconut, contributed to a

major share of the national income. More than half the population of 7 million were dependent on agriculture for a livelihood. The agriculture sector added to 40 percent of national revenue in 1948. There was little interaction between the plantation sector and the domestic non-plantation agricultural sector. The plantation sector performance dominated the activities of most other sectors of the economy such as trade and commerce, banking and insurance, transport and manufacturing activities, including the processing of the three plantation crops. The economy was open to free trade. Exports and imports accounted for about 70 percent of gross domestic product (GDP) (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2016). Now, Sri Lanka is capita income of USD 3,835 in 2016 which is underworld bank counties categories is in a lower-middle-income nation. Sri Lanka has a total population of 21 million people. Sri Lanka's economy has grown at 4.4 % in 2016. In 2016, the service sector has produced for 56.5% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), followed by manufacturing 26.8 %, and agriculture, 7.1 % (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2016).

Individual countries,(Changjun Zheng, 2010; Calderón & Liu,2003; Demetriades & Hussein, 1996; Atif, Jadoon, Zaman, & Ismail, 2007; Akinboade, 1998) and panels of countries,(King & Levine, 1993; Beck, Levine, & Loayza, 2000; Jung, 1986; Asghar & Hussain, 2014; Ahmed & Wahid, 2011) have been studied the association between financial development and economic growth using different methodologies. (Habibullah, 1999)(Sinha & Macri, 2001)(Choong, Yusop, & Soo, 2004)(Tang, 2005)(Asghar & Hussain, 2014). There are three kinds of results. The first one unidirectional relationship second one bidirectional relationship and third one no relationship at all. Studies of Sri Lanka have insufficient, There have different ideas on conclusions and one unique method they have applied the papers (R. Perera & Ichihashi, 2016) (N. Perera & Paudel, 2009) (Amarathunga, 2012) (U. W. B. M. Kumari, 2014). Among them, Rexiang and Rathanasiri (Rexiang & Rathanasiri, 2011) have the same method but additionally applied Engle-Granger dual step methodology.

The objective of this study is to examine the relationship between financial development and economic growth in Sri Lanka. To pursue this objective, this study has developed the following sub-objective to identify the factors affecting to the short term financial development and economic growth in Sri Lanka, to identify the factors affecting to the long term financial development and economic growth in Sri Lanka and to determine the open economic policy to change Sri Lankan financial development.

Materials and methods

This is a study which focuses on relationship between financial development and economic growth in Sri Lanka which is mainly expected to deal with quantitative data such as Gross Domestic Product, M2 Money Supply, Loans, Investment, Government Debt, Current A/C Balance, The Consumer Price Index and two dummy variables as Political Stability and Economic Stability.

This study adopted an explanatory approach by using a panel research design to fulfill the research objective. The advantage of using data is that it helps to study the behavior of each country over time and across space (Gujarati, 2003). Furthermore, data are commonly used because it consists of both the cross-sectional information which detentions individual variability and the time series data which captures dynamic adjustment in order to give more informative data. In other words, modeling supports to identify a common group of characteristics as well as heterogeneity among individual units. Based on theoretical and empirical literature on financial development and economic growth, figure 3.1 shows the conceptual framework of this study.

Figure 3.1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Compiled by author

The annual data set is employed for the Sri Lankan economy for the period 1948 to 2016. Gross Domestic Product, M2 Money Supply, Loans, Investment, Government Debt, Current A/C Balance, The Consumer Price Index are available from Annual Reports of Central Bank of Sri Lanka 1950 - 2016. The data is calculated in United States dollars. All the data are transformed into a natural logarithm.

Unit Root Test

As mention in the economic theory variable should be stationary before the application of standard econometric techniques. In this study, the unit root test for stationary was applied to evaluate the stationarity of the variables in the model. A stationary process or variable is a stochastic process whose parameters such as the mean and variance do not change over time or position. A variable whose observation changes over time or position is described as a nonstationary or having a unit root. Testing the stationarity of economic time series is of great importance since standard econometric methodologies assume stationarity in the time series while they are, in fact, non-stationary. Hence, based on two testable hypotheses (for each variable) are formulated as follows:

Null Hypotheses H_0 = Variable is not stationarity or has got unit root test

Alternative Hypotheses H_1 = Variable is stationarity or has not unit root test

Guideline: If P-value is more than 0.05 then the Null Hypothesis is accepted or the Alternative Hypothesis is rejected. If P-value is less than 0.05 then the Null Hypothesis is rejected or the Alternative Hypothesis is accepted.

Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

To decide among the short-run and long-run that can be used VECM. (Masih & Masih, 1996) (Engle & Granger, 1987) (Wooldridge, 2012)

Chow test

Due to an economic or political policy change or unexpected shock to the economy, it can be used Chow test. (Chow, 1960)(Gujarati, 2003)(Wooldridge, 2012). Here that can be used Chow Breakpoint Test for the check 1977 was a milestone or not?

Hence, based on two testable hypotheses (for each variable) are formulated as follows:

Null Hypothesis (H0) = No breaks at specified breakpoints (1977)

Alternative Hypothesis (H1) = breaks at specified breakpoints (1977)

Guideline: If P-value is more than 0.05 then the Null Hypothesis is accepted or the Alternative Hypothesis is rejected. If P-value is less than 0.05 then the Null Hypothesis is rejected or the Alternative Hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

Descriptive Statistics: This section shows the descriptive statistics of dependent and independent variables employed in the thesis for 69 years period of Sri Lanka. The dependent variables used in the study is Gross Domestic Product (GDP) while the independent variables are M₂ money supply (M2), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI), Economic Stability (ES) and Political Stability (PS). Thus, the total observations for each dependent and explanatory variable were 69. Table 4.1 presents the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, maximum values Skewness, Kurtosis, Jarque-Bera, its Probability, Sum and Sum Sq. Dev for the dependent and independent variables.

In this study, the unit root for stationary is applied to evaluate the stationary of the variables in the model. Table 4.2 shows the test for stationarity. The finding showed that all the variables are stationary at 5% levels of significance. The null hypothesis is the unit root and the alternative hypothesis is level stationery. The p-value of less or equal 5% significance level shows a rejection of the null hypothesis. Finding of this unit root test indicate that GDP, M2, INVEST, GD, CAB and CPI are in 1st and 2nd difference stationary and LOAN has only 2nd difference stationary. There is not any variable has passed for a unit root in level.

Lag Length Selection: Determining the optimum lag length is a critical issue in the cointegration and VECM analyses. A change in the lag length will completely change the results. In this thesis, the results of the lag length selection tests direct that many criteria and suggest a time lag of one as optimal. Therefore, the optimally selected time lag for the first difference is lag 1.

Johansen Test of Cointegration: Eight variables are used for the estimation of the cointegration namely, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Money supply (M2), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR). Optimal lag length is lag one. The null hypothesis of none, at most one and most six, is rejected at a five percent level, indicating that the

variables are cointegrated because that the variables have a common trend in the long run. More clearly explained, None mean there is no equation cointegrated. The Trace statistics (194.441) more than the critical value (159.5297) therefore it is rejected null hypothesis. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.0002. Then the probability value is less than 5%. Then the conclusion is rejected Null hypothesis meaning that the seven variables are not cointegrated. Then, at most one meaning that there is one equation cointegrated. The Trace statistics (128.7576) more than the critical value (125.6154) therefore it is rejected null hypothesis. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.0318. Then the probability value is less than 5%. Then the conclusion is rejected Null hypothesis meaning that the seven variables are not cointegrated. But, at most two meaning that there are two equations cointegrated. The Trace statistics (88.09577) less than the critical value (95.75366) therefore it is accepted null hypothesis. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.1497. Then the probability value is higher than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesis meaning that the seven variables are long-term associations. Then, at most three meaning that there are three equations cointegrated. The Trace statistics (53.84802) less than the critical value (69.81889) therefore it is accepted null hypothesis. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.4681. Then the probability value is higher than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesis meaning that the seven variables are cointegrated. After that, at most four meaning that there are four equations cointegrated. The Trace statistics (30.59242) higher than the critical value (47.85613) therefore it is accepted null hypothesis. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.6882. Then the probability value is higher than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesis meaning that the seven variables are long-term associations. Then, at most five meaning that there are five equations cointegrated. The Trace statistics (18.78487) higher than the critical value (29.79707) therefore it is accepted null hypothesis. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.5085. Then the probability value is higher than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesis meaning that the seven variables are cointegrated. Next, at most six means there are six equations cointegrated. The Trace statistics (9.224228) less than the critical value (15.49471) therefore it is accepted null hypothesis. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.3451. Then the probability value is less than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesis meaning that the seven variables are not long-term associations.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

	GDP	M2	LOAN	INVEST	GD	CAB	CPI
Mean	8.632	7.330	6.834	6.973	8.117	-4.390	5.550
Median	8.470	7.270	7.080	7.220	8.240	-5.370	5.020
Maximum	11.310	10.380	10.450	10.200	11.050	12.200	7.970
Minimum	6.460	5.010	3.210	4.110	4.770	-8.440	4.610
Std. Dev.	1.399	1.514	1.979	1.726	1.798	3.532	1.054
Skewness	0.355	0.366	0.030	0.172	-0.139	2.294	0.973
Kurtosis	2.040	1.971	1.934	1.999	1.920	9.510	2.558
Jarque-Bera	4.098	4.584	3.281	3.223	3.576	182.318	11.449
Probability	0.129	0.101	0.194	0.200	0.167	0.000	0.003
Sum	595.580	505.790	471.570	481.140	560.070	-302.940	382.950
Sum Sq. Dev.	133.082	155.792	266.252	202.476	219.824	848.532	75.599
Observations	69.000	69.000	69.000	69.000	69.000	69.000	69.000

Sources: Compiled by author

At last, at most seven means there are six equations cointegrated. The Trace statistics (3.88251) more than the critical value (3.841466) therefore it is rejected null hypothesize. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.0488. Then the probability value is less than 5%. Then the conclusion is rejected Null hypothesizes meaning that the seven variables are not long-term associations.

Table 4.1 Unit Root Test

Variable	Test Equation	Test for Unit Root in					
		Level		1st Difference		2nd Difference	
		t-Statistic	Prob.*	t-Statistic	Prob.*	t-Statistic	Prob.*
GDP	Individual Intercept	1.173	0.998	-9.381	0.000	-10.688	0.000
	Individual Intercept and Trend	-2.190	0.487	-9.772	0.000	-10.613	0.000
	None	5.461	1.000	-3.864	0.000	-10.778	0.000
	Conclusion	Non - Stationary		Stationary		Stationary	
M2	Individual Intercept	1.668	1.000	-11.260	0.000	-12.859	0.000
	Individual Intercept and Trend	-6.015	0.000	-11.246	0.000	-12.606	0.000
	None	3.231	1.000	-2.754895	0.007	-12.999	0.000
	Conclusion	Non - Stationary		Stationary		Stationary	
Loan	Individual Intercept	0.220	0.972	-8.260	0.000	-8.308	0.000
	Individual Intercept and Trend	-2.795	0.204	-8.188	0.000	-8.243	0.000
	None	7.206	1.000	-1.221	0.201	-8.381	0.000
	Conclusion	Non - Stationary		Non - Stationary		Stationary	
INVEST	Individual Intercept	0.312	0.977	-6.838	0.000	-9.500	0.000
	Individual Intercept and Trend	-3.317	0.072	-6.846	0.000	-9.417	0.000
	None	3.836	1.000	-7.138	0.000	-9.577	0.000
	Conclusion	Non - Stationary		Stationary		Stationary	
GD	Individual Intercept	-0.922	0.776	-8.952	0.000	-7.991	0.000
	Individual Intercept and Trend	-2.671	0.252	-8.895	0.000	-7.937	0.000
	None	7.300	1.000	-2.716	0.007	-8.055	0.000
	Conclusion	Non - Stationary		Stationary		Stationary	
CAB	Individual Intercept	-4.518	0.001	-9.131	0.000	-7.080	0.000
	Individual Intercept and Trend	-7.538	0.000	-9.059	0.000	-7.003	0.000
	None	-0.903	0.321	-9.173	0.000	-7.150	0.000
	Conclusion	Non - Stationary		Stationary		Stationary	
CPI	Individual Intercept	-1.664	0.445	-8.442	0.000	-7.470	0.000
	Individual Intercept and Trend	-1.603	0.782	-8.398	0.000	-7.423	0.000
	None	-0.521	0.487	-8.498	0.000	-7.534	0.000
	Conclusion	Non - Stationary		Stationary		Stationary	
AWDR	Individual Intercept	-1.117	0.705	-7.581	0.000	-7.801	0.000
	Individual Intercept and Trend	-2.248	0.456	-7.528	0.000	-7.733	0.000
	None	-0.423	0.527	-7.576	0.000	-7.866	0.000
	Conclusion	Non - Stationary		Stationary		Stationary	

Source: Compiled by author

Next one Maximum Eigen statistics. None mean there is no equation cointegrated. The Maximum Eigen statistics (65.68341) more than the critical value (52.36261) therefore it is rejected null hypothesize. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.0013. Then the probability value is less than 5%. Then the conclusion is rejected Null hypothesizes meaning that the seven variables are not cointegrated. Then, at most one meaning that there is one equation cointegrated. The Maximum Eigen statistics (40.66187) less than the critical value (46.23142) therefore it is accepted null hypothesize. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.175. Then the probability value is less than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesizes meaning that the seven variables are cointegrated. Next, at most two meaning that there are two equations cointegrated. The Maximum Eigen statistics (34.24775) less than the critical value (40.07757) therefore it is accepted null hypothesize. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.1959. Then the probability value is higher than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesizes meaning that the seven variables are long-term associations. Then, at most three meaning that there are three equations cointegrated. The Maximum Eigen statistics (23.2556) less than the critical value (33.87687) therefore it is accepted null hypothesize. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.511. Then the probability value is higher than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesizes meaning that the seven variables are cointegrated. After that, at most four meaning that there are four equations cointegrated. The Maximum Eigen statistics (11.80755) higher than the critical value (27.58434) therefore it is accepted null hypothesize. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.9402. Then the probability value is higher than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesizes meaning that the seven variables are long-term associations. Then, at most five meaning that there are five equations cointegrated. The Maximum Eigen statistics (9.560641) higher than the critical value (21.13162) therefore it is accepted null hypothesize. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.7848. Then the probability value is higher than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesizes meaning that the seven variables are cointegrated. Next, at most six meaning that there are six equations cointegrated. The Maximum Eigen statistics (5.341718) higher than the critical value (14.2646) therefore it is accepted null hypothesize. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.6982. Then the probability value is higher than 5%. Then the conclusion is accepted Null hypothesizes meaning that the seven variables are cointegrated. At last, at most seven means there are seven equations cointegrated. The Maximum Eigen statistics (3.88251)

more than the critical value (3.841466) therefore it is rejected null hypothesis. Same happen in probability test. The probability test is 0.0488. Then the probability value is less than 5%. Then the conclusion is rejected Null hypothesis meaning that the seven variables are not long-term associations. According to calculations seven, all other variables in the model have positive values except M2 and Loan variables have negative values. Its indication that M2 or Loan increases that GDP decreases. All other variables increase as a result of that GDP increases. Above statistic both Trace statistics and Maximum Eigen statistics, there are two cointegrating relationships in the long term. To explore association among variables this thesis uses the Economic Growth as the first cointegrated vector and the Financial Development as a second cointegrated vector. According to the variables are cointegrated, then VAR can be accomplished to check the path and degree of associations among all variables.

Vector Error Correction Model Test (VECM)

Dependent Variable Gross Domestic Product (GDP): The eight variables are used for the estimation of the VECM namely, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Money supply (M2), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR). Optimal lag length is lag one. According to calculations, it can be derived from the residual of the cointegration equation when GDP is the dependent variable.

$$\text{GDP} (-1) - 1.83817441941 * \text{M2}(-1) - 0.571358982815 * \text{LOAN} (-1) + 1.37932141869 * \text{INVEST} (-1) + 0.401980355247 * \text{GD} (-1) + 0.244320467405 * \text{CAB} (-1) + 0.108195165375 * \text{CPI} (-1) + 0.0304202767028 * \text{AWDR} (-1) - 3.69209097688$$

According to calculations, R^2 is 40.79 %, This means that 40.79 % of the total variation in the GDP is accounted for by the change in the Money supply (M2), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI), and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR). The system is a moderate fit. Because it is less than 60%. According to F-statistic is 5.8605 and its Prob(F-statistic) 0.0000, This means that the GDP can be influenced by the Money supply (M2), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR).

Long-Run Causality: According to the above equation, Speeds of adjustments towards long-run equilibrium is -0.0311. They are significant, and the sign should be negative. There is long-run causality from the seven independent variables such as Money supply (M2), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR). Meaning that seven variables influence the dependent variables such as GDP in the long run. In other words, there is long-run causality running from Money supply (M2), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR) to GDP.

Short Run Causality: Short-Run Coefficient means that Money supply (M2), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB) and The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR). In the short run coefficient statistically, a significant relationship between GDP and other individual variables at the 5% level of the significance level. Among these, M2 are statistically, a significant relationship to GDP. Other are not statistically, a significant relationship to GDP. Table 4.2 present the short-run causality in the system. According to table 4.2, M2 has short-run causality running from GDP.

Table 4.2 Short Run Causality (Dependent GDP)

Variable	Chi-square value	Probability	Short Run Causality
Money supply (M2)	14.05249	0.0002	Short Run
Loan (LOAN)	0.57169	0.4496	No Short Run
Investment (INVEST)	0.624564	0.4294	No Short Run
Government Debt (GD)	0.069982	0.7914	No Short Run
Current Account Balance (CAB)	0.533064	0.4653	No Short Run
Consumer Price Index (CPI)	0.612515	0.4338	No Short Run
Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR)	0.00291	0.957	No Short Run

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Dependent Variable Money supply (M2): The eight variables are used for the estimation of the VECM namely, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Money supply (M2), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR). Optimal lag length is lag one.

According to calculations, it can be derived from the residual of the cointegration equation when M2 is the dependent variable.

$$M2(-1) - 0.544018015615 * GDP(-1) + 0.310829580035 * LOAN(-1) - 0.750375701091 * INVEST(-1) - 0.218684555178 * GD(-1) - 0.132914735852 * CAB(-1) - 0.0588601191665 * CPI(-1) - 0.0165491785663 * AWDR(-1) + 2.00856400671$$

According to calculations, R^2 is 35.77 %, This means that 35.77 % of the total variation in the M2 is accounted for by the change in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI), and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR). The system is a moderate fit. Because it is less than 60%. According to F-statistic is 3.588948 and its Prob(F-statistic) 0.001323, This means that the M2 can be influenced by the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR).

Long-Run Causality: According to the above equation, Speeds of adjustments towards long-run equilibrium is 0.166565. They are significant, and the sign should be positive. There is not long-run causality from the seven independent variables such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR). Meaning that seven variables can not influence the dependent variables such as M2 in the long run. In other words, there is no long-run causality running from Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB), The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR) to M2.

Short Run Causality: Short-Run Coefficient means that Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Loan (LOAN), Investment (INVEST), Government Debt (GD), Current Account Balance (CAB) and The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR). In the short run

coefficient statistically, a significant relationship between M2 and other individual variables at the 5% level of the significance level. Among these, Government Debt (GD) and Current Account Balance (CAB) are statistically, a significant relationship to M2. Other are not statistically, a significant relationship to M2. Table 4.3 present the short-run causality in the system.

Table 4.3 Short Run Causality (Dependent M2)

Variable	Chi-square value	Probability	Short Run Causality
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	0.903197	0.3419	No Short Run
Loan (LOAN)	1.153211	0.2829	No Short Run
Investment (INVEST)	0.122166	0.7267	No Short Run
Government Debt (GD)	9.678927	0.0019	Short Run
Current Account Balance (CAB)	4.544638	0.0330	Short Run
Consumer Price Index (CPI)	0.000509	0.9820	No Short Run
Average Weight Deposit Rate (AWDR)	0.415568	0.5192	No Short Run

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Chow Test: Ten variables are used for the estimation of the chow test, namely, GDP, M2, LOAN, INVEST, GD, CAB, CPI, AWDR, ES, and PS. Null Hypothesis (H_0) is no breaks at specified Structural breakpoints in the 1977 or Alternative (H_1) is not.

According to calculation, the F- statistic is – 1.847949. Critical Value is – 2.04. Then the Null Hypothesis is rejected, or the Alternative Hypothesis is accepted.

Therefore, 1977 was a landmark position because of free trade has been started from that year.

The Relationship Between Financial Development and Economic Growth in Sri Lanka

Based on the methodology, this thesis discussed to accomplish the goal and solved the research problem. The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between financial development and economic growth in Sri Lanka and to achieve it successfully. The one-way relationship between Sri Lanka and its confirmation from financial sector development to GDP was proposed.

Other sub-objectives

Chapter one is given other specific objectives. They are to exam the reasons for association about short-term financial development and economic growth in Sri Lanka, to exam the reasons for the association between long-term financial development and economic growth in Sri Lanka and to determine the open economic policy to change Sri Lankan financial development .First, Under the factors affecting the short-term financial development and economic growth in Sri Lanka. The conclusion of the 1st sub-objective is reconfirmed that M2 and economics stability are significant in Sri Lanka. Then identify the factors affecting the long-term financial development and economic growth in Sri Lanka. The adjusted R2 value is 99 percent, and the F test is also provided this model is an acceptable model. Finally, determine the open economic policy to change Sri Lankan financial development. Yes, it had. The year 1977 was a landmark in the economics and social policies of the post-independence period. Far-reaching policy reforms were introduced in the year to shift the focus from an inward-looking development strategy to an outward-looking development strategy to free the economy from an array of controls.

Suggestions for Future Studies

This study aims to examine the relationship between financial development and economic growth of nine variables. As mentioned in the section on limitations, some suggestions can be made for future studies. There are other macroeconomic variables example saving, real interest rate, effective tax rate, savings, liquid liabilities, that may affect finance and GDP. Also, this thesis used VECM and Chow test. There are many advanced methods such as fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) and PDOLS for analyzing the data.

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No

Dedication

No

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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